

THE CONDENSATION OF α -SUBSTITUTED ACETOACETATES WITH PHENOLS. PART VII THE CONDENSATION OF VARIOUS SUBSTITUTED PHENOLS WITH ETHYL ACETOSUCCINATE.

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In continuation of Part VI, ethyl acetosuccinate has been condensed with various substituted phenols, having -COOMe, CO-R (R=Me, Ph), -NO₂, halogens as substituents. The effect of these substituents on the course of the reaction has been discussed.

In the preceding part of this series (Part VI), the authors showed that ethyl acetosuccinate condenses with different phenols giving the coumarin-3-acetic acid derivatives. With a view to study the effect of different substituents in a phenol molecule, the condensation of ethyl acetosuccinate with several substituted phenolic derivatives was undertaken and the results are described in this part. The reactivity of the following substituents -COOMe, COMe, CO.Ph, -NO₂ and halogens on the course of the reaction has been studied.

Methyl β -resorcyolate on condensation with ethyl acetosuccinate in the presence of sulphuric acid gives methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (Shah, Sethna *et al*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 717). The expected ethyl 7-hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate could not be obtained in spite of several attempts. It may be pointed out that the group CH₂COOEt is eliminated in this condensation as in case of *m*-cresol described in the previous part. Phosphoryl chloride also gives the same product in lesser yield.

2-Acetyl-resorcinol easily undergoes the condensation in presence of sulphuric acid as well as phosphorus oxychloride. Sulphuric acid is found to hydrolyse the product giving the coumarin-3-acetic acid directly; while the oxychloride gives ethyl 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methyl coumarin-3-acetate which on hydrolysis gives the above acid, identical with the Fries migration product of 7-acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate (*vide* previous paper). This condensation of 2-acetyl-resorcinol was studied by Shah and Jatti (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1940, 65) in presence of aluminium chloride with the production of identical coumarin derivatives.

Similarly, 2-benzoyl-resorcinol smoothly undergoes condensation yielding ethyl 7-hydroxy-8-benzoyl-4-methyl coumarin-3-acetate.

Resacetophenone and resbenzophenone do not condense with ethyl acetosuccinate. The deactivating effect of acyl group in 2-position of the resorcinol nucleus is negligible; whereas the same in the 4-position is very great as resacetophenone and other 4-acyl-resorcinols do not condense even with unsubstituted acetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid (Sethna, Shah and Shah. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228, 1424 and subsequent papers).

In order to find the effect of nitro group, the condensation of 2- and 4-nitro-resorcinols was tried but unchanged phenols were recovered.

Clayton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 2018) generalised that the presence of halogen atom in the phenolic nucleus hinders the Pechmann reaction. It seemed, therefore, of interest to study the behaviour of halogenated phenols with ethyl acetosuccinate. 4-Chloro-phenol, 4-chloro-*m*-cresol, 4-chloro-resorcinol, 4-bromo-resorcinol and 4-chloro- α -naphthol have been tried. 4-Chloro-phenol does not condense: this is in conformity with the usual less reactivity of *para*-substituted phenols in the Pechmann reaction. All the remaining halogenated phenols condense with ethyl acetosuccinate giving the corresponding coumarin-3-acetic acid derivatives. It is interesting to note that 4-bromo-resorcinol gives ethyl 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin-3-acetate. This elimination of bromine during the condensation is noteworthy. As far as we are aware, it is a singular instance of halogen elimination in the Pechmann reaction.

From the results described here and in the previous part, it is found that the classification of phenols with regard to their reactivity with β -ketonic esters in Pechmann reaction holds good in case of ethyl acetosuccinate also. *m*-Cresol and β -naphthol give coumarins in good yields. No chromone derivative has been obtained in any case even with less reactive phenols in presence of phosphorus pentoxide. It is evident from the results that in spite of the heavier bulk of its α -substituent, the acetosuccinate is equally or even more reactive than the corresponding simple α -alkyl substituted acetoacetate. The introduction of the negative group like carboethoxy in the alkyl group has tended to increase the reactivity of the ester which may be attributed to its greater enolisation. Similar observations have also been made in case of the Pechmann condensation of phenols with ethyl α -acetoglutarate, the next homologue of ethyl acetosuccinate (Shah and Shah, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 2075).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Methyl β -resorcylate with Ethyl acetosuccinate.—Methyl β -resorcylate (4g.) was mixed with ethyl acetosuccinate (5 g.) and sulphuric acid (80% ; 25 c.c.) gradually added. The mixture was left overnight and worked up as usual. A pasty mass separated, and on washing with little alcohol it gave a white solid, which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 213-214°, yield 3 g., mixed m.p. with methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate was unchanged.

The condensation was repeated several times under different conditions to get the expected coumarin-3-acetic acid but the product obtained was identical with the above, the elimination of CH_2COOEt taking place.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 172-173°, mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

Condensation of 2-Acetyl-resorcinol: Formation of Ethyl 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methyl-coumarin-3-acetate.—To the mixture of 2-acetylresorcinol (1 g.) and ethyl acetosuccinate (1.5 g.), phosphorus oxychloride (2 c.c.) was added with cooling and after about 20 hours, it was worked up; the yellowish solid was collected and crystallised from alcohol as needles, m. p. 167°-168°. (Found: C, 63.1; H, 5.4. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 63.2; H, 5.3 per cent). The coumarin dissolves in alkali with non-fluorescent yellow colour and gives violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.⁹

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as thin plates, m. p. 221-223°. (Found: C, 63.3; H, 5.1. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 62.5; H, 5.2 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the above Ester.—The ester (0.5 g.) was treated with 2 *N*-sodium hydroxide (10 c.c.) on a water-bath for about 20 minutes. It was cooled and acidified; the solid crystallised from alcohol as needles, m. p. 262-263°. (Found: C, 60.8; H, 4.7. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 60.9; H, 4.4 per cent). 7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic acid gives wine-red colour with ferric chloride.

The same acid was directly obtained by condensing 2-acetyl-resorcinol in presence of 80% sulphuric acid.

Condensation of 2-Benzoylresorcinol: Formation of Ethyl 7-Hydroxy-8-benzoyl-4-methyl coumarin-3-acetate.—2-Benzoyl-resorcinol (1 g.), ethyl aceto-succinate (2 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (2 c.c.) were condensed as in the preceding case. The product was crystallised from alcohol as rectangular plates, m. p. 196-197°. (Found: C, 65.92; H, 4.85. $C_{21}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 65.97; H, 4.7 per cent). The coumarin is soluble in common organic solvents and dissolves in alkali with non-fluorescent yellow colour and gives red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as rhombic crystals, m. p. 177°. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 4.8. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 65.1; H, 4.7 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-8-benzoyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic Acid.—The ester (1 g.) was mixed with 2 N-sodium hydroxide (25 c.c.) and kept at room temperature for 24 hours. It was then acidified and the solid dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution, filtered and the filtrate acidified; the acid crystallised from dilute alcohol as small needles, m. p. 255°. (Found: C, 64.3; H, 4.0. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 64.4; H, 3.9 per cent).

Condensation of 4-Chloro- α -naphthol: Formation of 6-chloro-4-methyl-1:2- α -naphthopyrone-3-acetic Acid and its Ethyl Ester.—To the mixture of 4-chloro- α -naphthol (4 g.) and the ester (5 g.) concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) was gradually added with shaking and cooling. The product, isolated as before, crystallised from alcohol as needles, m. p. 185-86°, yield 2 g. Chakravarti and Bagchi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 655) give m. p. 181-184°. (Found: Cl, 11.05. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ Cl: Cl, 10.75 per cent).

The ester was hydrolysed as before. The acid crystallised from acetic acid as needles, m. p. 276-277°. (Found: Equiv., 301.7; Cl, 11.85. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ Cl requires Equiv., 302; Cl, 11.73 per cent). The same acid was obtained directly if the condensation was carried out using 80% sulphuric acid.

The anilide crystallised from alcohol as thin lustrous needles, m. p. 265-66°. (Found: Cl, 9.5. $C_{23}H_{16}O_4$ NCl requires Cl, 9.4 per cent).

Condensation of 4-Chloro-resorcinol: Formation of 7-Hydroxy-6-chloro-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic Acid and its Ethyl Ester.—To the mixture of resorcinol (2.5 g.) and ethyl aceto-succinate (4 g.), concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) was added with cooling in ice. The product obtained as before crystallised from acetic acid as small needles, m. p. 174°. Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 626) gives the same m. p. The coumarin gives intense blue fluorescence in alkaline solution.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as needles, m. p. 169°. (Found: Cl, 10.65. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ Cl requires Cl, 10.49 per cent).

Phosphorus oxychloride also effects this condensation.

The above ester was refluxed with 2 N-sodium hydroxide (20 c.c.) for about $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour. The acid was isolated as usual and crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles, m. p. 263°. (Found: Cl, 13.14. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ Cl requires Cl, 13.2 per cent).

Condensation of 4-Bromoresorcinol.—4-Bromo-resorcinol was prepared according to method described in *Org. Syn.* (1937, 17, 23). To the mixture of resorcin (4 g.) and ethyl aceto-succinate (5 g.), phosphorus oxychloride was slowly added with cooling. The mixture was worked up as before. The product obtained was found to be ethyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate, the de-bromination having occurred during the course of the reaction. Sulphuric acid as condensing agent gave an uncrystallisable product.